

KEY INDICATORS

With 46,007 hectares, Norway had 4.7% of its farmland under organic management, less than half of the area share of the European Union, of which Norway is not a member. Growth from 2001-2022 was at 72%, thus one of the lowest among the countries analyzed here. In Norway, organic retail sales amounted to 460 million euros; data on organic retail sales shares is not available.

ORGANIC FARMLAND

2001

2022

Area* (Share of Total Farmland)

26,673 ha (2.6%)

46,007 ha (4.7%)

Area Growth from 2001 to 2022

72%

ORGANIC LAND USE & AQUACULTURE

2001

2022

Arable Land* (Share of Total)

5,356 ha (0.6%)

10,067 ha (1.3%)

Permanent Crops* (Share of Total)

96 ha (3%)

358 ha (12%)

Grassland* (Share of Total)

21,379 ha (13.3%)

34,334 ha (19.1%)

Aquaculture Production (Share of Total)

N/D

239 t (5.2%)

ORGANIC OPERATORS

2001

2022

Producers (Share of Total)

2,099 (3%)

1,974 (5.1%)

Aquaculture Producers

N/D

94

Processors

377

459

Importers

22

127

ORGANIC RETAIL SALES

2001

2022

Retail Sales (Share of Total)

N/D

460 M€

Per Capita Consumption

N/D

84.6 €

Retail Sales Growth from 2001 to 2022

N/D

Imports

N/D

N/D

Source: FIBL survey based on national data sources, Eurostat and TRACES/European Commission in the framework of the OrganicTargets4EU project

*In conversion and fully organic

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DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC FARMLAND IN NORWAY

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey based on Norwegian Agricultural Authority, Debio, Eurostat, Nic Lampkin

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC RETAIL SALES IN NORWAY

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey based on Norwegian Agricultural Authority and further national data sources

ORGANIC POLICY SUPPORT

Norway is not a member of the European Union, and therefore does not implement the Common Agricultural Policy, but it does have similar support mechanisms for conversion to and maintenance of organic farming. However, no data was obtained for the 2018 or 2027 years that are the focus of this factsheet series.

NATIONAL ORGANIC ACTION PLAN

The current organic action plan in Norway runs from 2018 to 2030. It has no specific headline targets. Previous action plans were not analysed in this study.

KEY ACTIONS

PREVIOUS ACTION PLAN (NONE)

No previous plan

PRODUCTION

No previous plan

MARKETS

No previous plan

INFORMATION

CURRENT ACTION PLAN (2018 - 2030)

Support for conversion and organic production

Supply chain co-ordination to grow market; engage with public procurement and hospitality catering, including information and advisory support; maintain regulatory committee for standards, R&D and advice

Consumer information; Food Nation Norway campaign; provide advice through Norwegian advisory service, with focus on products in demand; promote organic content in schools, vocational and higher education to contribute to skilled workforce; support research, development and innovation; address specific technical issues; involve all parts of supply chain

AQUACULTURE

In Norway, organic aquaculture production is mainly directed towards salmon. In 2020 the total production of organic salmon was 25,546 t, almost 2% of total salmon production. Details of policy support for organic aquaculture were not identified.

Sources for page 3

Lampkin N, Lembo G, Rehburg P (2024) *Assessment of agricultural and aquaculture policy responses to the organic F2F targets*. OrganicTargets4EU project Deliverable 1.2. Braunschweig: Thünen-Institut.

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